

IMPROVING THE ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC FOUNDATIONS OF ENSURING FOOD SAFETY.

Usmanov Sardorbek Beg'amovich

Termiz Institute of Agrotechnologies and Innovative Development

Teacher of the department of agribusiness, accounting and digital technologies.

Abstract: In this article, it is necessary to look at food safety as a multi-level system with clearly structured goals on hierarchical levels. According to the entities solving this problem, global, inter-regional, inter-state, state, local, population groups and family (households), i.e. 7 levels can be distinguished.

Key words: Food, economic fundamentals, global problem, households.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolda oziq-ovqat xavfsizligiga iyerarxiya darajalari bo'yicha aniq tarkiblashtirilgan maqsadlarga ega bo'lgan ko'p darajali tizim sifatida qarash zarur. Mazkur muammoni hal qiluvchi subyektlarga ko'ra global, xududlararo, davlatlararo, davlat, mahalliy, aholi guruhlari va oila (uy xo'jaliklari), ya'ni 7 ta darajalarini ajratib ko'rsatishi mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: Oziq ovqat, iqtisodiy asoslar, global muammo, uy xo'jaliklari.

Аннотация: В данной статье необходимо рассматривать безопасность пищевых продуктов как многоуровневую систему с четко структурированными целями на иерархических уровнях. По субъектам, решающим данную задачу, можно выделить глобальные, межрегиональные, межгосударственные, государственные, местные, группы населения и семьи (домохозяйства), т.е. 7 уровней.

Ключевые слова: Продовольствие, основы экономики, глобальная проблема, домохозяйства.

International organizations and special bodies (FAO, International Trade Organization, Food Safety Committee) solve the problem of food safety on a global

(world) scale. Their main task is to help stabilize the economy of countries in order to ensure human development. Implementation of these tasks:

- development and implementation of long-term programs and projects affecting production volume;
- is carried out by creating reserves and organizing assistance in unfavorable economic and environmental situations.

The main goal of food security at the state and international level is the sustainable development of the economy and the balancing of food product markets.

The main goal at the regional level is to provide all groups of the population with a level of income that guarantees that food is consumed in accordance with established standards.

At the level of social groups (families) of the population, it is necessary to ensure that food products are consumed in accordance with rational standards in terms of their quantity, assortment, and quality.

Management of this process at each level of food safety should be carried out by the relevant administrative bodies. The tasks of these bodies are for efficient production of necessary products; so that the population living in the areas belonging to them have an income that allows them to buy the recommended amount of products; to ensure the delivery of food products to trade networks; is to create conditions to control the quality and safety of products.

Solving food problems at the international level is related to helping to eliminate food shortages in other countries. For this, countries participate in interstate cooperation, contribute to the creation of international food security. In doing so, they should develop their competitive production and self-sufficiency of regions and all social groups (for example, the CIS).

Each level of food security is formed under the influence of internal and external factors that are interrelated and mutually demanding.

Ensuring the balance of demand and supply in the domestic food market, forming the state fund, and stabilizing economic development are reflected in the state's policy aimed at ensuring food security.¹

Achieving food security requires the implementation of the following important tasks by the state:

1. Creation of stable economic conditions;
2. Conduct effective agrarian policy;
3. Creating equal opportunities for all business entities;
4. To carry out an effective policy in the field of population employment;
5. Conduct social policy aimed at eliminating inequality and poverty in access to food;
6. Achieving diverse, stable and intensive production of food products, increasing its efficiency;
7. Support the introduction of advanced technologies in the production and processing of raw materials and food products;
8. Self-sufficiency of regions with raw materials and food products and improvement of agricultural placement and specialization, using the advantages of international division of labor effectively;
9. Active foreign economic policy, optimization of export-import activities;
10. Investing in the agricultural sector.

List of used literature.

1. Ismatullayev P.R. "Fundamentals of metrology". Study guide. Tashkent. 2012.
2. Ismatullayev P. R., Torayev SH.A., Hamrokulov G'.Kh. Quality management system and it sertifikatlash O'quv qo'llanma. -T. Toshkent. 2014.
3. Choriyev A.J Oziq-ovqat maxsulotlari menejmenti xavfsizligi fanidan elektron o'quv-uslubiy majmua matni // Metodik qo'llanma, T.: TKTI, 2013. – 328 b.